

KINETICS OF THE ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF CHLOROFORM IN ETHANOL

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The order of the reaction, as determined by isolation and integration methods, has been found to be 2, when alkali concentration is not more than 2 or 3 times that of chloroform. Specific rate constants evaluate between 20° and 40°. The Arrhenius energy of activation, determined graphically, is 33.3 K. cal. in 95% ethanol. In presence of a large excess of alkali, the order has been found to increase to 3.

Saunders (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1900, 4, 660) found the rate of hydrolysis of chloroform by alkali in 95% ethanol to be of first order with respect to both hydroxide and chloroform concentrations. Abel (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1923, 29, 391) reported that in very dilute solutions the reaction was of the first order, being independent of alkali concentration, but with an increase in alkali concentration the order was found to increase. Hine (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2438) using aqueous dioxane solutions found the reaction to be bimolecular. In view of this divergence in kinetic order, the present investigation was undertaken, using 95% ethanol solutions. An analytical study of this reaction (Bose, this *Journal*, 1949, 36, 554) reveals that two simultaneous reactions take place during alkaline hydrolysis :

At temperatures below 45°, the first reaction is predominant while at higher temperatures, the second one occurs to a larger extent, involving the evolution of a large quantity of carbon monoxide. Hence, a kinetic study was undertaken at temperatures below 45°.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard solution of chloroform was prepared by weighing the Analar variety of the reagent and dissolving it in absolute ethanol (C.P.). The alkali was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and diluted with the same solvent. This solution was standardised with 0.05*N*-HCl after keeping for 24 hours and then used. In most of the experiments the reaction was followed by estimating the KOH content by titration with HCl (0.05*N*) to phenolphthalein end-point. In presence of a large excess of alkali, the KCl produced was evaluated by Vohlard's method. The reaction was stopped in all the experiments by acidifying the solution with HCl or HNO₃. In some experiments, a large quantity of KCl precipitated out which made pipetting difficult. This difficulty was overcome by thermostating aliquoted portions.

Order of Reaction.—The velocity of reaction may be represented by the equation :

$$-dc/dt = k_1 C_1^m C_2^n \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where C_1 and C_2 represent respectively the concentration of KOH and CHCl₃. In the following series of experiments, a large excess of chloroform was used so that during the course of the reaction its concentration diminished by about 1.5%, whereas that of KOH to less than half. Hence, the concentration of the former may be taken as practically constant. The velocity equation then takes the following form :

$$-dc/dt = (k_1 C_2^n) C_1^m = k_2 C_1^m \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where $k_2 = k_1 C_2^n$. The order of the reaction is the same as m . It appears from Table I that the values of k_2 calculated for $m = 1$ exhibit such a degree of constancy that the equation indicating a unimolecular order with respect to KOH may be regarded as the appropriate one.

TABLE I

Apparent first-order rate constants in presence of excess of CHCl₃.

Time (min.)	Initial conc. of CHCl ₃ = 1.25M. Temp. = 25°.								
	0	10	32	79	133	199	300
KOH conc. (N×200)	9.5	9.0	8.0	6.8	5.4	4.2	2.7
k × 10 ⁴ (unimol.)	41.7	42.7	42.3	42.5	41.2	41.9
Mean k × 10 ⁴	at 25.		at 30.		at 35.		
			42.0		81.9		178.0		

Determination of n.—Supposing in equation (2) k'_1 and k''_1 are the two values of k_1 (in the equation $k_1 = kC_2^n$) obtained in two experiments in each of which C_1 , the initial concentration of KOH, is the same whilst the concentrations of chloroform are different; say C'_2 and C''_2 , the following equations are obtained:

$$k'_1 = kC'^n_2 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$k''_1 = kC''^n_2 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

If logarithms are taken and results subtracted, it is found, that

$$n = \log \frac{k'_1}{k''_1} / \log \frac{C'_2}{C''_2} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

The values of k'_1 and k''_1 have been found by assuming $m = 1$ in the velocity equation (2). The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Apparent first-order constants in presence of two diff. conc. of CHCl₃ (in excess).

Temp.	Initial conc. of CHCl ₃ = 0.6 M.	Initial conc. of CHCl ₃ = 1.2 M.
	Mean $k'_1 \times 10^4 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	Mean $k''_1 \times 10^4 \text{ min.}^{-1}$
25°	16.2	34.4
30°	36.0	74.0
35°	75.0	163.0

By combining the above results, the actual values of n found are 1.08, 1.03 and 1.12 at 25°, 30° and 35° respectively. n appears to approach very closely to the value 1. Hence, the reaction in presence of excess of chloroform is unimolecular with respect to both the reacting substances.

Values of n and m in presence of excess of KOH.—Using a large excess of KOH and assuming $n = 1$ in equation (1), unimolecular constants were calculated. The constancy of the values obtained indicates a unimolecular order with respect to CHCl₃. By using two different concentrations, C'_1 and C''_1 for KOH (in excess) (cf. Table III), the value of m was calculated according to equation (5), substituting m for n and C_1 for C_2 . Strangely enough, the values of m found were 1.97 and 1.96 at 25° and 30° respectively. Therefore in presence of excess of KOH, the reaction is unimolecular with respect to CHCl₃ and bimolecular with respect to KOH. This is in agreement with the observations of Abel (*loc. cit.*) who reports that the order with respect to KOH increases with increase in its concentration.

TABLE III

Apparent first-order rate constants in presence of two diff. conc. of KOH (in excess).

Temp.	Mean $k_1' \times 10^4 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	Mean $k_2' \times 10^4 \text{ min.}^{-1}$
25°	107	27.4
35°	444	114.0

* Refers to initial concentrations of the reactants.

Bimolecular Rate Constants.—The stoichiometric equation for the reaction at lower temperatures is

When a , b , $a - x/4$ and $b - x$ are the initial and instantaneous concentrations of CHCl_3 and KOH respectively, the rate equation is

$$dx/dt = k(a - x/4)(b - x).$$

The integrated form is

$$kt = \frac{4}{b - 4a} \cdot \ln \frac{a(b - x)}{b(a - x/4)} \quad \dots (6)$$

Taking dilute solutions of the two reactants in proportions other than stoichiometric, the rate of disappearance of alkali was found at different temperatures (20°-40°). A plot of \log of $b - x / (a - x/4)$ against time was found to be a straight line as expected from equation (6). The rate constants, calculated for several temperatures and those at 35°, are shown in Table IV. The k was found to be fairly constant for a particular run. The effect of change in concentration and relative proportion of the reactants was also studied and a slight but distinct fall in k was noticed with decrease in the alkali concentration, as recorded in Table V.

TABLE IV

Bimolecular rate constants at 35° using diff. initial conc. of the reactants.

Time.	$b - x$ ($M \times 10^2$).	$a - x/4$ ($M \times 10^2$).	$k \times 10^4$ ($\text{l.mol}^{-1} \times \text{min}^{-1}$).	Time.	$b - x$ ($M \times 10^2$).	$a - x/4$ ($M \times 10^2$).	$k \times 10^4$ ($\text{l.mol}^{-1} \times \text{min}^{-1}$).
0 min.	18.41	9.99	..	0 min.	9.205	4.992	..
60	16.74	9.57	163	60	8.814	4.890	137
120	15.29	9.20	162	121	8.423	4.835	141
226	13.16	8.68	162	242	7.825	4.653	140
317	11.59	8.32	164	318	7.490	4.576	139
403	10.40	8.01	162	405	7.098	4.472	138
499	9.20	7.69	162	500	6.680	4.370	153
617	7.90	7.36	163	1118	4.680	3.864	140
			Mean 162				Mean 141

TABLE V

Effect of relative proportion and conc. of the reactants on k at 35°.

Ratio of CHCl_3 : KOH . (Molarity basis).	Initial conc. of KOH .	$k \times 10^4$ ($\text{l.mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$).	Divergence from mean.
1 : 1.2	0.12 N	150	-5.0%
1 : 1.8	0.092	141	-11
1 : 1.8	0.14	158	Nil
1 : 1.8	0.19	162	+0.3
1 : 2.5	0.25	168	+5.0
1 : 3.7	0.28	169	+7.0
		Mean 158	

Temperature Dependence.—The effect of variation in temperature on the rate of the reaction

FIG. 1

was studied between 20° and 40° using the same initial concentration of the two reactants (CHCl_3 , 0.1M; KOH , 0.2M). In Fig. 1, $\log k$ (bimolecular) has been plotted against $1/T$, and from the slope of the straight line obtained, the Arrhenius activation energy of 33.3 K. cal. was calculated. From the expressions of the transition state theory (Glasstone, Eyring and Laidler, "Rate Processes", 1941, pp. 197, 417) the values of the heat and entropy of activation were computed for the reaction at 25° when $k = 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ l. mol}^{-1} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$. These quantities are $\Delta H = 32.7 \text{ K. cal.}$ and $\Delta S = 44 \text{ e.u.}$

DISCUSSION

Hine (*loc. cit.*) has presented a strong case in favour of the view that the hydrolysis of chloroform by alkali commences with the extraction of the proton by the basic anion. The bimolecular reaction in ethanol also appears to follow the same mechanism:

The fact that the order of the reaction increases with the increase in alkali concentration is undeniable. In presence of a large excess of KOH , the termolecular reaction observed cannot be regarded as merely a medium effect. It is very likely that the hydroxyl ions, when in excess, not only extract a proton but substitute one of the halogen atoms by hydroxyl:

The formation of carbon monoxide, as indicated in the mechanism postulated by Hine (*loc. cit.*), was found to be negligible (Bose, *loc. cit.*) in presence of large concentrations of alkali. This fact also lends support to the mechanism shown above.

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